
VIOLET TEAMING AI IN THE LIFE SCIENCES

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Abstract

As modern life science research shifts from an observational field of science to a field of engineering biology, computational techniques are more relevant to every aspect of the field. Artificial intelligence (AI) is emerging as a massive accelerator of biological engineering for its ability to learn the design paradigms of life (DPoL) and understand the genotype-to-phenotype (G2P) relationships of organisms. The reception has been mixed, however, as opportunities across health, energy, environment, agriculture, and industrial materials are confronted with emerging biosecurity risks across novel pathogens of concern and operational knowledge of biological engineering. There is an urgent need for research to be conducted at the intersection of AI security and biosecurity and the establishment of a violet teaming paradigm where research focused on risk is paired with those focused on the opportunity to minimize the downside and maximize the upside provided by AI in the life sciences.

Keywords Artificial Intelligence · AI Security · Engineering Biology · Synthetic Biology · Biosecurity

1 Design paradigms of life and the genotype-to-phenotype relationship

The majority of research and product development in the life sciences relies on understanding and manipulating biological systems. Unlike other engineering disciplines, biology occurs naturally and has been evolving independently of human intervention for millions of years. Convergent evolution, however, shows us that life is not as random as it may seem, and that underlying genetic diversity is a set of design paradigms of life (DPoL). These design paradigms are effectively the biological design rules that underpin biological function. The quest to understand these design paradigms is focused on understanding the genotype-to-phenotype (G2P) relationships across plants, animals, insects, and microorganisms.

An organism's genotype is its genetic code, and its phenotype is how that genetic code is expressed as a physical or functional trait. For example, a phenotype of dogs is their fur and a phenotype of viruses is the way they replicate within a host. There is wide variation in genotypes that lead to variation in phenotypes, but there is also conserved genotypes that can lead to similar form and function across organisms. Again for example, the fur of most dogs or the similar way many viruses replicate.

2 Changes to the genotype-to-phenotype relationship

Much of the biomedical research field focuses on understanding disruptions to the G2P relationship and how that leads to diseases such as cancer and diabetes. In the infectious disease space, research is often focused on how viruses, bacteria, and fungi mutate their genotypes over time to create new phenotypes that allow the invader to evade the immune system, and how to develop new drugs to keep pace with these mutations.

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In the biotechnology field, genetic engineering tools like CRISPR are rapidly being developed to intentionally edit and engineer DNA to create a desired novel phenotype (Jinek et al. 2012). The engineering biology and synthetic biology industry uses these techniques to manipulate the genotype of microorganisms, such as metabolism, so that their new phenotypes can produce new products across industrial materials, energy, health, food and agriculture, and environmental applications (Benner and Sismour 2005).

3 Synthetic biology and biosecurity concerns

As with any new technology, the opportunities and excitement are met with concerns about heightened risks from intentional and unintentional misuse of the technology. The field of biosecurity is a well-established industry focused on preventing and combating the emergence and spread of infectious disease through methods such as inventory process management, physical security, personnel reliability, material transport programs, and information security. As biological engineering is maturing and new methods are being developed, there is a concern of the expanding risk of infectious diseases with heightened transmissibility, lethality, and drug resistance as well as the emergence of novel phenotypes that cause new or more severe diseases.

In 2018, for example, a researcher from the University of Alberta synthesized an extinct horsepox, a cousin of small pox, for a relatively modest cost in a university lab (Noyce, Lederman, and Evans 2018). This application of modern biotechnology demonstrated the ability to synthesize sequences of concern. And while this example did not include the intentional engineering of additional phenotypes into this virus, the biosecurity community is leery of the increasing accessibility of technologies to make this possible.

One method that is employed to prevent the engineering of pathogens of concern is DNA sequence screening at the point of synthesis. Many commercial companies that provide DNA synthesis services implement screening methods, but at the moment in the United States, adherence to screening standards is voluntary on the part of the organization providing these services.

4 Artificial intelligence in the life sciences

At the same time that engineering biology techniques are expanding rapidly, artificial intelligence (AI) is making massive steps in capability improvement across all industries. The growth of popularity of deep learning techniques, now commonly referred to as AI, emerged in 2012 and progressed rapidly over the course of the next decade. Early work with AI in the life sciences demonstrated promise of these models to learn latent representations of biology (DPoL) ahead of our ability to measure as much (Titus, Bobak, and Christensen 2018; Way and Greene 2017).

In just the past few years, however, the advent of the transformer model architecture and its underpinning of large language models (LLMs) has created a paradigm shift in AI capabilities that is now causing dual optimism and concern in the life sciences. These advances are most likely a brief step in a rapidly progressing industry where innovation is released nearly hourly at this point.

AI models such as DeepMind’s AlphaFold learned the DPoL for protein folding and generated predictions on structure for every known protein (Jumper et al. 2021). An effort that experimentally would take years and thousands of dollars, if it was possible at all. Facebook’s DNABERT has expanded our understanding of the genotypic relationships within DNA sequences and is being applied widely (Ji et al. 2021). In industry, unconventional collaborations are forming, such as the \$50M investment from NVIDIA, an AI hardware company, into Recursion Pharmaceuticals, a computational drug discovery company. The promise for AI to accelerate our understanding of the G2P relationships in biology will unlock unprecedented capabilities to develop new products and drugs.

The same tools that are accelerating our understanding of biology are also increasing our ability to engineer products of concern as well as democratizing access to the operational knowledge of doing so. In a 2022 example, researchers reversed a common goal of drug discovery, minimize drug toxicity, and leveraged AI to optimize drug toxicity (Urbina et al. 2022). The result produced 40,000 predicted toxins of concern, including some similar to VX, the most potent nerve agent known to date. There is a growing concern that modern AI models are increasingly learning to represent biological DPoL, and can allow users to manipulate the G2P relationship of infectious diseases for harmful purposes. AI also unlocks the ability to do this at scale, predicting the structure, function, and production methods of far more compounds than possible manually.

New products, however, are only one part of the issue. In an example demonstrated by researchers at MIT, LLMs increase novice and non-experts ability to access the knowledge of developing dual-use biotechnologies

(Soice et al. 2023). The concern is that, unlike the Canadian expert that synthesized the extinct horsepox virus in an academic lab, many more people will have the ability to do the same with less training, understanding of the risks, or barriers to do harm. There is a concern that LLMs and other AI models can help users circumvent DNA sequence screening policies and will democratize operational knowledge of biology and reduce the barrier for users to build existing but regulated infectious diseases.

5 Digital biosecurity

In response to these emerging concerns there is policy and legislation being introduced, such as a recent AI security framework from the Biden-Harris administration (White House 2023) and the Artificial Intelligence and Biosecurity Risk Assessment Act and Strategy for Public Health Preparedness and Response to Artificial Intelligence Threats Act by Senators Markey and Budd to study and quantify the risks of AI in the life sciences (Edward J. Markey and Ted Budd 2023). There is an urgent need for rigorous science in digital methods for biosecurity. These areas would include AI security, cybersecurity, and information security (Titus, Hamilton, and Holko 2023).

Across all of these domains, there is also a risk of over regulating and halting technology progress unnecessarily. While there is a small but growing number of researchers red teaming the risks of AI in the life sciences, there is a larger number of researchers blue teaming this intersection. But to date, there are not enough, if any, researchers developing methods of violet teaming AI in the life sciences.

5.1 Red, blue, purple, and violet teaming

Red teaming is the practice of studying threats, blue teaming is the practice of studying and developing defensive measures, and purple teaming is a method of pairing researchers focused on understanding the possible threat vectors of a technology, in this case AI in the life sciences, with researchers working to build defensive technologies to those risks (Oakley 2019). Violet teaming takes one step farther and pairs red and blue teams together to also build resilient systems that minimize harm to an institution of public benefit using the very technology that is generating the security concerns (Titus and Russell 2023). The concept comes from the AI security industry, where teams work in tandem to identify vulnerabilities and build tools to mitigate them at the same time. This often leads to building methods to use the very tools that are posing the most risk to prevent the risks (Aviv Ovadya 2023).

6 Violet teaming AI in the life sciences

Violet teaming AI in the life sciences would involve research such as leveraging AI models that are capable of generating sequences of concerns to screen against the sequences that models generate to prevent them from being generated in the first place. For example, a LLM that is capable of leveraging its learned representation of the design paradigms of viruses can be used to identify when the G2P relationship has been altered to suggest increased virulence and lethality, and can prevent the model from generating that sequence. In essence, this can be thought of as a generative digital sequence screening method that is upstream of the traditional sequence screening methods employed by DNA synthesis providers.

7 A need for AI security in the life sciences

There is a risk of over regulating AI applications in the life sciences because of the potential risks that are created by the powerful models that have emerged in the past year, and will emerge and an increasing rate going forward. Let's not throw the baby out with the bathwater, however, and let's exercise caution to ensure we retain the valuable elements while addressing the specific issues. The opportunity space is immense, and one opportunity is to mitigate the risks posed by AI in the life sciences.

In addition to the example above of leveraging AI as a generative digital sequence screening method, the same model that represents pathogen design paradigms can be leveraged to develop medical countermeasures that are specifically engineered to identify, recognize, and respond to such pathogens. Even major funders of pandemic preparedness, such as CEPI, are leveraging AI to speed up vaccine development against Disease X (CEPI 2023). This is a prime opportunity for violet teaming AI for vaccine development. We can build new biology to protect us while reducing the likelihood of new biology that poses significant risk to us. We can also leverage AI models to predict how bad actors may circumvent biosecurity protocols, such as DNA sequence screening policies, and build resiliency into such policies.

There is a lot more research that is required to confidently build the AI security techniques that reduce the risks while capturing the opportunities. There are AI researchers that care to prevent the misuse of AI, and there are engineering biology researchers that want to prevent the misuse of biotechnology. But due to the complexity of both fields, these are rarely the same researchers or even the same lab. By bringing experts in AI security, biosecurity, and engineering biology together under the same research goals, we can grow a cadre of researchers trained at the intersection of these technologies and that will unlock the future benefits of engineering biology while reducing the risks of its misuse.

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